

Contribution to the knowledge of Coleoptera of Albania: seven new records

A.I. Gubin¹, O.V. Pak²

¹Donetsk Botanical Garden

Illich pr., 110, Donetsk, 283023, DPR, Russia

e-mail: helmintolog@mail.ru

ORCID 0000-0001-7599-5012

²R. Luksemburg str., 21-5, Donetsk, 283050, DPR, Russia

e-mail: olegpak@bk.ru

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Abstract. Seven Coleoptera species from 5 families are newly recorded from Albania, providing the first documented evidence of their occurrence in the country.

Introduction

The entomofauna of Albania currently remains among the least studied in Europe. It is evident that the numerous gaps in our knowledge of the country's insect fauna can be addressed only through systematic and comprehensive investigations. Nevertheless, given the present state of research, even isolated and fragmentary data are of substantial scientific value.

During an entomological expedition to Albania conducted from 3 to 23 May 2021 by A.I. Gubin (Donetsk), O.V. Pak (Donetsk), Yu.Ye. Skrylnyk (Kharkov) and I.G. Plyushch (Kiev), several beetle species previously unrecorded from Albania were discovered. Some of these findings were published earlier in a contribution devoted to longhorn beetles (Cerambycidae) (Lazarev & al., 2024). The present paper reports the first records of seven species of Coleoptera new for the fauna of Albania.

Material and methods

All materials were identified by the authors except *Sphenoptera (Deudora) gemmata gemmata* A.G. Olivier, 1790,

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which identified by its collector Yu. Skrylnyk.

Photos were taken by A.I. Gubin using Nikon D7200 camera with Nikon 105mm f/2.8G IF-ED AF-S VR Micro-Nikkor lens. Mounted specimens were photographed using Carl Zeiss Stemi 2000-C microscope with Zeiss AxioCam Erc 5s camera. Photos were stacked, improved for contrast and brightness using Adobe® Photoshop®CS5 and Adobe Photoshop Lightroom Classic 2020 v9.2.1.10 software. Photo on fig. 9 was made by Yu.Ye. Skrylnyk using Canon EOS 6D camera with Canon EF-S 60mm f/2.8 Macro USM lens and C-AF 13mm extension tube.

Results

Family Glaphyridae Macleay, 1819

Pygopleurus apicalis (Brullé, 1832)

Figs 1-2

Material examined. 12 exs., Albania, Gjirokastrë County, 1.6 km N Saraqinishtë vill., Lunxherise Mts., 40°07'08.07"N, 20°13'32.78"E, 916 m, 07-08.V.2021, A.I. Gubin leg.; 14 exs., the same data but I. Plyushch leg.; 5 exs., the same data but Yu. Skrylnyk leg.; 1 ex., Albania, Vlorë County, 17 km NNW Sarande, S env. of Lukove vill., 39°59'0.38"N, 19°54'47.61"E, 150 m, 06.V.2021, O. Pak leg.

Remarks. The species is known from Greece, North Macedonia, southwestern Bulgaria, and southern Serbia (Nikodým & Bezděk, 2016; Bollino et al., 2019; Byk et al., 2023). Examined specimens were collected in flowering meadows within open montane woodland (Fig. 2), where they were found inside the flowers of *Papaver* sp. (Fig. 1), together with another related species *Pygopleurus chrysonotus* (Brullé, 1832).

Family Scarabaeidae Latreille, 1802

Oxythyrea dulcis Reitter, 1899

Figs 3-4

Material examined. 4 exs., Albania, Lezhë County, Lezhë distr., 6 km NW Shëngjin, Buna River-Velipoja Protected Landscape, 41°50'16.05"N, 19°31'52.70"E, 5 m, 13.V.2021, O. Pak leg.; 5 exs., the same data but Yu. Skrylnyk leg.; 17 exs., the same locality but

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22.V.2021, A.I. Gubin leg.; 11 exs., the same data but O. Pak leg.; 8 exs., the same data but Yu. Skrylnyk leg.

Remarks. The species is known from Greece, Montenegro and Turkey (Bezděk, 2016; Vondráček et al., 2018; Byk et al., 2022). Examined specimens were collected in coastal sand dunes (Fig. 4) on the inflorescences of *Cyperus capitatus* Vand. (Fig. 3).

Family Buprestidae Leach, 1815

***Sphenoptera (Deudora) gemmata gemmata* A.G. Olivier, 1790**

Figs 9, 12

Material examined. 2 males, Albania, Vlorë County, 3.5 km E Vagalat, 39°45'43.02"N, 20°9'39.46"E, 81 m, 06.V.2021, Yu. Skrylnyk leg. et det.

Remarks. According to Cobos (Cobos, 1986), the species is distributed in Southern Europe from Portugal and Spain to Former Yugoslavia, and in North Africa from Morocco to Egypt and Asia Minor. However, according to current data, the species is reliably known from Egypt, Algeria, Morocco, Tunisia, Spain, Portugal, Southern France, Italy (including Sicilia - as *Sphenoptera (D.) gemmata sicelidis* (Obenberger, 1916) and Croatia (Kalashian & Sakalian, 2007; Kalashian, 2016). The species' presence in other countries of the former Yugoslavia and in Greece requires confirmation. Examined specimens were collected in a plain covered with broom (*Genista* sp.) bushes (Fig. 12).

***Sphenoptera (Deudora) signata* Jakovlev, 1887**

Figs 5-6

Material examined. 3 exs., Albania, Vlorë County, 7.5 km S Kaninë, Lungar Mts., 40°23'37.45"N, 19°31'10.09"E, 810 m, 16.V.2021, A.I. Gubin leg.; 1 ex., Albania, Gjirokastrë County, 8 km ENE Gjirokastrë, Saraqinisht vill. env., Lunxherise Mts., 40°06'51"N, 20°13'36"E, 830 m, 07.V.2021, O. Pak leg.

Remarks. The species is known from Bulgaria, North Macedonia, Greece, Turkey, Israel, Syria, Iran, Turkmenistan, Georgia, Armenia and Azerbaijan (Kalashian & Sakalian, 2007; Kalashian, 2016). Examined specimens were collected in mountain meadow (Fig. 6).

Figs 1-2. *Pygopleurus apicalis* (Brullé, 1832): 1 - couple on *Papaver* sp. flower, 2 - locality: Albania, Gjirokaštër County, 1.6 km N Saraqinishtë vill., Lunxherise Mts., 40°07'08.07"N, 20°13'32.78"E, 916 m., 08.05.2021.

Figs 3-4. *Oxythyrea dulcis* Reitter, 1899: 3 - imago on *Cyperus capitatus* Vand. inflorescence, 4 - locality: Albania, Lezhë County, Lezhë distr., 6 km NW Shëngjin, Buna River-Velipoja Protected Landscape, 41°50'16.05"N, 19°31'52.70"E, 5 m., 22.05.2021.

Figs 5-6. *Sphenoptera (Deudora) signata* Jakovlev, 1887: 5 - imago, 6 - locality: Albania, Vlorë County, 7.5 km S Kaninë, Lungar Mts., 40°23'37.45"N, 19°31'10.09"E, 810 m., 16.05.2021.

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Family Meloidae Gyllenhal, 1810

***Meloe (Taphromeloe) erythrocnemus* Pallas, 1782**

Figs 7-8

Material examined. 1 ex., Albania, Vlorë County, 4.5 km S Kaninë, Lungar Mts., 40°23'57.34"N, 19°31'5.06"E, 757 m, 05.V.2021, A.I. Gubin leg.; 1 ex., the same data but Yu. Skrylnyk leg.; 1 ex., the same locality but 16.V.2021, I. Plyushch leg.

Remarks. The species is widely distributed from the Apennine Peninsula and North Africa to western China (Bologna, 2020). Examined specimens were collected in mountain meadow (Fig. 8).

Family Curculionidae Latreille, 1802

***Curculio venosus* Gravenhorst, 1807**

Fig. 10, 13

Material examined. 1 ex., Albania, Dibër County, Bulqizë Municipality, 1.5 km W Ostren I Madh vill., 41°25'34.01"N, 20°26'15.42"E, 1148 m, 12.V.2021, A.I. Gubin leg.

Remarks. The species is widely distributed in Europe and is also known from North Africa, Turkey, Transcaucasia and Afghanistan (Caldara, 2013; Alonso-Zarazaga et al., 2017). Examined specimen was collected in open montane woodland on *Quercus pubescens* Willd. (Fig. 13).

***Curculio villosus* Fabricius, 1781**

Figs 11-13

Material examined. 2 exs., Albania, Dibër County, Bulqizë Municipality, 1.5 km W Ostren I Madh vill., 41°25'34.01"N, 20°26'15.42"E, 1148 m, 12.V.2021, Yu.Ye. Skrylnyk leg.

Remarks. The species is widely distributed in Europe and is also known from North Africa, Turkey and Israel (Caldara, 2013; Alonso-Zarazaga et al., 2017). Examined specimens were collected in open montane woodland on *Quercus pubescens*. (Fig. 13).

Figs 7-8. *Meloe (Taphromeloe) erythrocnemus* Pallas, 1782: 7 - imago, 8 - locality: Albania, Vlorë County, 4.5 km S Kaninë, Lungar Mts., 40°23'57.34"N, 19°31'5.06"E, 757 m., 05.05.2021.

Figs 9, 12. *Sphenoptera (Deudora) gemmata gemmata* A.G. Olivier, 1790: 9 - male, 12 - locality: Albania, Vlorë County, 3.5 km E Vagalat, 39°45'43.02"N, 20°9'39.46"E, 81 m, 06.05.2021.

Figs 10-11, 13. *Curculio* spp.: 10 - *Curculio venosus* Gravenhorst, 1807, imago, 11 - *Curculio villosus* Fabricius, 1781, imago, 13 - locality: Albania, Dibër County, Bulqizë Municipality, 1.5 km W Ostren I Madh vill., 41°25'34.01"N, 20°26'15.42"E, 1148 m., 12.05.2021.

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